

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D10.2 - Review of Effectiveness and Impact of Outreach and Stakeholder Engagement

WP10 – Dissemination and Outreach
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Executive summary

EOSC-Life is a complex project that began with 12 work packages and expanded to 14 as the project progressed. The project also brought together the 13 life science research infrastructures on the ESFRI roadmap and involved a total of 50 partners by the project's end. The stakeholders were identified early in the project as spanning a broad range of focus areas, and a considerable amount of thought was invested in planning subsequent outreach efforts to optimise communication.

Milestone **MS32**, the Strategic Marketing and Communication Plan, enabled the identification of key stakeholders that would be the target of the communication efforts, as well as the clear definition of the communication means and goals. Milestone **MS33**, Stakeholder Mapping, then allowed the stakeholders to be preliminarily categorised into 30 categories, and different communication strategies to be defined for these categories, depending on whether they were broadly recognised as stakeholders who were key players, needed to be kept informed, kept satisfied, or merely monitored.

Deliverable **D10.1**, the Strategic Marketing and Stakeholder Mapping Report, provided an updated overview of the information initially provided in **MS32** and **MS33**. This was based on input received from the work packages during the first half of the project and considered changes in communication strategies and tools that became necessary due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The input received resulted in an updated Stakeholder Map, featuring 24 stakeholder categories in 4 broad groups, which was used for the remainder of the project.

This Deliverable **D10.2** presents an updated Stakeholder Map based on work package leader feedback and reviews the effectiveness and impact of outreach and stakeholder engagement due to work package communication efforts throughout the project. We highlight communication strategies and methods ultimately identified as the most effective with the stakeholder categories, emphasising the impact of in-person versus online methods. Finally, we compare the communication targets established one year after the onset of the project (March 1, 2020) with the status achieved near the end of the project (July 1, 2023) to demonstrate our achievements.

Introduction

EOSC-Life was a cluster project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme from 1 March 2019 through 31 August 2023. This project brought together the 13 life science research infrastructures (LS RIs) on the ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) roadmap with the aim to create an open collaborative space for digital biology: The consortium successfully achieved this aim. EOSC-Life published FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) life science data resources for cloud use, creating an easily accessible ecosystem of innovative tools in the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). The project thus supported ground-breaking, data-driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to the EOSC.

The project was organised as depicted below in **Figure 1**. This figure illustrates the clear division made between the work packages shown in the middle, which ensured the “technical” access to the digital data space created in EOSC-Life, and more “service-oriented” work packages, which ensured access to this space, as well as the complex relationships between them.

Figure 1: EOSC-Life Work Packages

The project evolved considerably over the 4.5-year span from March 2019 to August 2023 and involved numerous marketing and communications actions. The effectiveness of these actions was assessed at the mid-point of the project (see **D10.1**) and is reviewed again in this deliverable, outlining the changes that occurred throughout the project.

By the mid-point of the project, it became necessary to adjust the initial stakeholder mapping due to the addition of two COVID-19-related work packages and general developments in the project. Subsequent developments in the project also resulted in adjustments to the mapping to reflect additional stakeholders and shifts in the prioritisation of these stakeholders where necessary. These changes are described in detail below.

During the second half of the project, based on feedback from the midterm review, a special emphasis was placed on disseminating project results as they were released to maximise the benefit of the project for all stakeholders. These dissemination actions were performed in close collaboration with each work package, placing a focus on the release of “success stories” to highlight (sustainable) project achievements.

This outreach was carried out to increase the visibility of the project activities and developments, as well as to attract additional potential users in the second half of the project. These goals could be achieved by actively encouraging transparent and internal communication within the RIs and coordinating intensive external communications among the consortium participants and their main stakeholders.

Project Objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached 4 of its objectives in Work Package 10:

- a. Ensure that all stakeholders were made aware of the project's aims, goals, and context in relation to the specific role of the participating LS RIs in a coherent and controlled way through the development of a strategic communication map.
- b. Ensure the promotion and dissemination of project deliverables to all stakeholders through the involvement of each participating RI and the generation of a communication tool kit.
- c. Provide active support for the dissemination, visibility, and attractiveness of publicly organised events during the project.
- d. Provide strategic outreach to other projects and relevant initiatives to support the implementation of demonstrators developed.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Development of the Strategic Marketing Plan

Early in the project, work package (WP) leaders recognised that more information about the main EOSC-Life stakeholders was needed to define and support the communication strategy. These stakeholders were identified and grouped (i.e., mapped) in the first year of the project. This stakeholder mapping was subsequently evaluated and revised at the mid-point of the project (see **D10.1**) and in this deliverable. Mapping these stakeholders and creating bridges of communication among them enabled us to prepare appropriate outreach material which was subsequently disseminated via a variety of communication channels (e.g., social media, internal and external newsletters, attendance to conferences, scientific publications).

The stakeholder landscape, needs, and expectations, as well as the EOSC-Life project environment, changed significantly over the 4.5-year project period – particularly due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, monitoring and revising the initially created stakeholder map was vitally important to ensuring the success of the communication efforts. As an example, 2 additional WPs were added in response to the COVID-19 pandemic (WP13 “Extension of COVID-19 Data Portal: core portal development and operationalisation of the extended portal through deep support and integration services” and WP14 “Design, development, implementation and use of a repository for individual participant data from COVID-19 trials). These additional stakeholders

were described, evaluated, weighted, and placed on the EOSC-Life stakeholder map as described in **D10.1**, and the communication strategy was revised accordingly.

The position of certain stakeholders on the map also shifted over time, in part due to our communication efforts and in part due to organisational changes. These changes altered both the impact of these stakeholders on the project and their interest in (supporting) the project. The recognition of these changes enabled us to alter our communication strategies to continue to ensure the success of the outreach.

For these reasons, it is helpful to briefly review in this deliverable how the stakeholder mapping developed over the course of the project.

1.1. Initial Stakeholder Mapping Efforts

An **initial stakeholder mapping exercise** was carried out as described in **Milestone MS33** for our work package in the first year of the project. In this exercise, a stakeholder map produced in the H2020 project CORBEL, in which the same 13 Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS-RIs) as in EOSC-Life participated, was used as an initial baseline. This map was distributed to each RI director, who was then asked to review the stakeholder categories and note where stakeholder categories should be shifted to a different group, due to the unique EOSC-Life project goals.

The 4 stakeholder groups initially used in the CORBEL project were deemed equally useful in the EOSC-Life project and carried over, comprising (1) **Key Players**, (2) **Keep Informed**, (3) **Keep Satisfied**, and (4) **Monitoring** groups.

The **Key Players** were defined as stakeholders who were integral to the success of the project due to their high degree of power (i.e. within the RI or within the EOSC landscape) and interest in the project goals. It was considered essential to meet the stakeholders' needs and involve them in discussions and in decision-making processes.

The **Keep Informed** stakeholders were highly interested in the project but had little real power to execute any actions. Communication actions for this group were designed to encourage their involvement in the project and to consult with them on topics of their interest.

The **Keep Satisfied** stakeholders, in contrast, had potential power to execute actions within the project, but had little interest in the project and its goals. The communication actions were designed to meet the stakeholders' needs and enable them to provide feedback; at the same time, efforts were made to increase their overall interest in the project to shift them to the 'Key Players' group.

The **Monitoring** stakeholders had little power over the project or interest in the project. For this reason, communication actions for this group were designed to provide a minimal amount of information on the project's progress and outcomes and not to overwhelm them with details. As with the Keep Satisfied group, efforts were made throughout the project to increase the interest of these stakeholders in the project, i.e., here to shift them to the 'Keep Satisfied' group.

The success of the outreach in increasing the interest of certain groups of stakeholders and their action levels is described in more detail in later sections of this deliverable. The initial stakeholder mapping exercise resulted in the production of the table of EOSC-Life stakeholders (Table 1)

shown below (see Milestone **MS33** for definitions of these groups, comments, and more detailed information):

Key players (high power, high interest)	Keep informed (high interest, low power)	Keep satisfied (low interest, high power)	Monitoring (low interest, low power)
Participating RIs (Hubs and Nodes)	Disease-, food- and biotechnology-/pharma-oriented scientific communities	Legal, regulatory, and normative institutions/authorities	RI users working in academia/research (data/sample providers)
Member States (Board/Assembly/Council Delegates)	Research institutes incl. technology transfer units	Research funders	RI users working in a clinic as healthcare professionals or researchers
EU/ESFRI	RI users working in industry	EOSC Executive Board, EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, and EOSC Governance Board	Media (including journal publishers)
Executive Board	Ethics committees		Associations
LS RI Strategy Board	Supra-/international organisations		Health research agencies outside Europe
Scientific and Ethic Advisory Board	Industrial technology developers and manufacturers		
E-Infrastructure Advisory Board	Lobbying groups		
EOSC Cluster Projects	European research community at large		
EOSC Portal Providers	Communities of software developers		
	Patient organisations		
	Horizon Europe programme committees		
	EU infrastructure/infrastructure projects		
	Other EOSC projects and EOSC Regional Clusters		

Table 1: Initial map of EOSC-Life stakeholders (status: Jan/Feb 2020)

This mapping was used in the first half of the project to establish communication means and frequency, as well as to identify contact persons within each category.

1.2. Mid-term assessment of stakeholder mapping

At the project mid-term, a survey was sent out to representatives of each work package to collect feedback on the strategic marketing and stakeholder mapping efforts from January 2020 – January 2021 and guide the development of communication actions for the remainder of the project. More detailed information about the survey and how it was carried out is provided in **D10.1**. Specifically, WP representatives were asked to **rank the stakeholders** shown in Table 1 *from the perspective of their work package* and to share information about additional stakeholders who had been identified as important in the first project year. Finally, they were

asked to list **3 stakeholder categories that they considered especially important** to reach during the remainder of the project.

The results of the survey are shown below in Table 2. The stakeholders are displayed in this table in the order that they were prioritised by WP leaders from top to bottom. Green shading indicates stakeholders that were prioritised by 2 or more WPs, whereas light yellow indicates those prioritised by 1 WP. The remainder were not prioritised by any work package.

Key players (high power, high interest)	Keep informed (high interest, low power)	Keep satisfied (low interest, high power)	Monitoring (low interest, low power)
Participating RIs (Hubs and Nodes)	Disease-, food- and biotechnology/pharma-oriented scientific communities	Legal, regulatory, and normative institutions/authorities	RI users working in academia/research (data/sample providers) * ↑
EOSC Cluster Projects ↑	European research community at large ↑	Research funders	RI users working in a clinic as healthcare professionals or researchers ↓
EU/ESFRI	RI users working in industry	EOSC Executive Board, EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, and EOSC Governance Board	Media (including journal publishers)
EOSC-Life Executive Board	Communities of software developers		Associations
LS RI Strategy Board	EU infrastructure/infrastructure projects		Health research agencies outside Europe
Member States (Board/Assembly/Council Delegates)	Industrial technology developers and manufacturers		
E-Infrastructure Advisory Board	Research institutes incl. technology transfer units		
EOSC Portal Providers	Supra-/international organisations		
EOSC Association (new)	Horizon Europe programme committees		
Scientific and Ethic Advisory Board	Ethics committees		
	Patient organisations		
	Lobbying groups		
	Other EOSC projects and EOSC regional clusters		

Table 2: Revised EOSC-Life stakeholder map based on survey results (status: Jan 2021)

*WP6 indicated that this category should be moved to group “Keep satisfied”

↑ = increased in importance ↓ = decreased in importance as compared to ranking in Table 1

The survey results were then considered in light of the feedback received from the **Midterm Review Report**, namely, to reduce the number of mapped stakeholders. As a result, stakeholders that were not prioritised by the work packages were removed, and stakeholders were shifted to different groups as suggested. This yielded an updated stakeholder map:

Key players (high power, high interest)	Keep informed (high interest, low power)	Keep satisfied (low interest, high power)	Monitoring (low interest, low power)
Participating RIs (Hubs and Nodes)	Disease-, food- and biotechnology/pharma-oriented scientific communities	Legal, regulatory, and normative institutions / authorities	RI users working in a clinic as healthcare professionals or researchers
EOSC Cluster Projects	European research community at large	Research funders	
EU/ESFRI	RI users working in industry	EOSC Executive Board, EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, and EOSC Governance Board	
EOSC-Life Executive Board	Communities of software developers	RI users working in academia / research (data/sample providers)	
LS RI Strategy Board	EU infrastructure/infrastructure projects		
Member States (Board/Assembly/Council Delegates)	Industrial technology developers and manufacturers		
E-Infrastructure Advisory Board	Research institutes incl. technology transfer units		
EOSC Portal Providers	Supra-/international organisations		
EOSC Association (new)	Horizon Europe programme committees		
Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB)			

Table 3: Revised EOSC-Life stakeholder map based on survey results and Midterm Review Report feedback (status: June 2021)

1.3. End-term assessment of stakeholder mapping

In July 2023, WP representatives were again asked to **review and rank the stakeholders** shown in Table 3 *from the perspective of their work package* and to share information about additional stakeholders who had been identified as important in the period of February 2021 – June 2023. For the final project communication and outreach efforts, it was crucial to update the EOSC-Life stakeholder mapping. This would ensure sustainable outreach of the LS RI achievements to the relevant communities beyond the project duration (e.g., as dissemination efforts of the RIs or stakeholder outreach efforts in other relevant projects). It was of particular interest to receive

feedback from these representatives regarding their perceptions of the stakeholder ranking and how this changed during the second half of the project.

This feedback enabled the creation of the updated stakeholder map shown below (Table 4). Again, green shading indicates stakeholders that were prioritised by 2 or more WPs, whereas light yellow indicates those prioritised by 1 WP.

Key players (high power, high interest)	Keep informed (high interest, low power)	Keep satisfied (low interest, high power)	Monitoring (low interest, low power)
Participating RIs (Hubs and Nodes)	Disease-, food- and biotechnology/pharma-oriented scientific communities	Legal, regulatory, and normative institutions / authorities	*Communities of software developers ↓
EOSC Cluster Projects	European research community at large	Research funders	RI users working in a clinic as healthcare professionals or researchers
EU/ESFRI	RI users working in industry	*E-Infrastructure Advisory Board ↓	**International counterparts providing FAIR life science data resources
EOSC-Life Executive Board	EU infrastructure/ infrastructure projects	RI users working in academia/research (data/sample providers)	
LS RI Strategy Board	Industrial technology developers and manufacturers	*Member States (Board/ Assembly/Council Delegates) ↓	
*EOSC Executive Board, EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, and EOSC Governance Board ↑	Research institutes incl. technology transfer units		
EOSC Portal Providers	Supra-/international organisations		
EOSC Association (new)	Horizon Europe programme committees		
Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB)			
**EU Data Spaces Working Groups & projects			

Table 4: Revised EOSC-Life stakeholder map based on 2nd survey results (status: July 2023)

*Shift in ranking (cf. Table 3) suggested by one or more WP

**Indicates additional stakeholder categories that were identified in the 2nd project half.

↑ = increased in importance ↓ = decreased in importance as compared to ranking in Table 3

A comparison of Tables 1–4 reveals how a total of **26 stakeholder categories** vital to the project’s success were identified over time, and how the ranking of these categories changed over the project duration.

Most WP representatives felt that the stakeholder rankings identified by the project mid-term still applied by the end of the project. Exceptions included a suggestion made to reduce the ranking of the **communities of software developers** (WP2: “Keep informed” to “Monitoring”), of the E-Infrastructure Advisory Board (WP4: “Key Player” to “Keep Satisfied”), and of the Member States (Board/Assembly/Council Delegates) (WP4: “Key Player” to “Keep Satisfied”). WP4 also suggested increasing the ranking of the EOSC Executive Board, EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, and EOSC Governance Board from “Keep Satisfied” to “Key Player”. These changes were suggested based on observations made as the project progressed. The categories of **RI users** and especially **researchers/research groups** were also ranked by more than one WP as becoming more important as the project progressed, shifting from the “Monitoring” to the “Keep satisfied” group.

Two new stakeholder categories of **EU data spaces working groups & projects** and **International counterparts providing FAIR LIFE science data resources** were also identified and ranked in the “Key Player” and “Monitoring” groups, respectively, in the 2nd project period.

2. Communication Objectives for Stakeholder Groups

2.1. Developments in stakeholders and communication objectives

The results of the mid-term survey and feedback from the Midterm Review Report were used at the project midpoint to create an updated map of stakeholders and prioritise these (see **Table 4, D10.1**). This enabled WP10 to preliminarily assess the amount of communication effort that should be invested in them and set clear outreach objectives.

During the second half of the project, communication and dissemination actions were designed to meet the outreach objectives defined for each of the stakeholders. Based on feedback received from WP representatives, an updated table (**Table 5**) of stakeholder categories with their descriptions and ranking is provided below, highlighting the communication objectives met in the second half of the project. The objectives initially defined in **D10.1** could be met through the strategic use of internal and external communication tools and channels.

#	STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	OBJECTIVE MET	GROUP
1	Participating RIs, Hubs and Nodes; Partners and Linked Third Parties	Participants in the EOSC-Life consortium	Informed regarding all project activity, enabling them to meet needs and requirements; dissemination of important information to nodes/hubs/network, helping them to find end users; applicants for critical LS Open Calls attracted	Key Players

2	LS RI Strategy Board	According to DoA (Description of Action) and CA (Consortium Agreement)	Strategies aligned; kept informed of project progress	Key Players
3	Executive Board (of EOSC-Life)	According to DoA and CA	Kept informed of project progress to support decision-making	Key Players
4	EOSC Association	Legal entity, MoU with EC to advance Open Science	Strategies aligned	Key Players
5	EU/ESFRI	EU and ESFRI group	Strategies aligned	Key Players
6	EOSC Executive Board, EOSC Executive Board Working Groups, and EOSC Governance Board		Strategies aligned	Key Players
7	EU Data Spaces Working Groups & projects		Informed about developments in the EU Data Spaces relevant for the LS RIs (e.g. the European Health Data Space), ensuring development of interoperable and complementary solutions	Key players
8	EOSC Cluster Projects	ENVRI-FAIR, PaNOSC, ESCAPE, SSHOC	Joint Stakeholder Forum coordination performed, overlapping activities aligned, cross-dissemination actions carried out to ensure the continuity of the collaboration in follow-up projects (e.g. OSCARS)	Key Players
9	EOSC-Life Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board	According to DoA and CA	Kept informed of project progress; input on strategy, scientific, and ethical issues sought	Key Players
10	EOSC Portal Providers		Kept informed of project progress	Key Players
11	Disease-, food- and biotechnology/pharma-oriented scientific communities	e.g. OERTC, EVER	Kept informed of project progress; applicants for Digital Life Science Call for Sensitive Data attracted	Keep Informed
12	Research institutes incl. technology transfer units	Associations with connected independent research institutions, universities	Kept informed of project progress; applicants for Digital Life Science Call for Academia-Industry Collaborations attracted	Keep Informed
13	RI users working in industry		Applicants for Digital Life Science Call for Academia-Industry Collaborations attracted	Keep Informed

14	Supra-/international organisations	e.g. WHO, UN, OECD, UNESCO, WMA	Kept informed of project progress	Keep Informed
15	Industrial technology developers and manufacturers	New instrumentation, technologies, software, etc. providers	Kept informed of project progress; applicants for Digital Life Science Call for Academia-Industry Collaborations attracted	Keep Informed
16	European research community at large		Kept informed of project progress	Keep Informed
17	Horizon Europe Programme Committees		Kept informed of project progress	Keep Informed
18	EU Infrastructure / Infrastructure projects		Kept informed of project progress	Keep Informed
19	Legal, regulatory, and normative institutions / authorities	Institutes involved with ELSI issues, certification, ABS	Requirements satisfied; applicants for Digital Life Science Call for Sensitive Data attracted	Keep Satisfied
20	Research funders	National research funders (DFG, BBSRC), other national research councils, non-profit organisations (Gates Foundation)	Requirements fulfilled to keep satisfied	Keep Satisfied
21	Member States	Countries (ministries) being a member state of a participating RI	Requirements satisfied to ensure continued RI funding; project updates provided; key interests identified	Keep Satisfied
22	RI users working in academia/research	RI users working in academia and research institutions	Project updates provided; applicants for all Digital Life Sciences Open Calls attracted	Keep Satisfied
23	E-Infrastructure Advisory Board		Project updates provided	Keep Satisfied
24	RI users working in a clinic as healthcare professionals or researchers		Applicants for Digital Life Science Call for Sensitive Data attracted	Monitor
25	Communities of software developers		Applicants for Cloud Data Deployment Call attracted	Monitor
26	International counterparts providing FAIR Life science data resources	International organisations and projects (e.g. NFAIS COPO)	Promote long-term aim of creating global data space for the life sciences	Monitor

Table 5: Updated EOSC-Life stakeholder categories with description and objectives

Yellow shading indicates a change in ranking identified in the 2nd project period.

2.2. End-term assessment of populating the stakeholder categories

As the EOSC-Life project progressed, WP representatives steadily identified contacts in defined stakeholder categories and disseminated the outreach materials as they were created via a variety of communication channels, including targeted emails, dedicated team communication tools (e.g. Microsoft Teams, Slack), virtual meetings and events, and the electronic external newsletters and social media channels of consortium members. Work package leaders and RI representatives were successfully able to expand their contact lists for these stakeholder groups, and especially those of strategic interest to specific consortium members, for targeted outreach during the second half of the project.

The creation of an **outreach toolkit** as part of the WP3 First Digital Life Sciences Call with sample email texts supported these efforts in that each person could send the modified email out to their own contacts. Due to the success of this approach, which attracted many applications, this strategy was reapplied for subsequent Open Calls. As EOSC-Life-supported calls, training actions, and networking events were held, these had the added advantage of attracting participants who populated these stakeholder groups and who made their acquaintances aware of the project (i.e. snowball effect). While most members of the “Key Players” group were made aware of the EOSC-Life project from the point it was launched, many stakeholder populations in the “Keep Satisfied”, “Keep Informed” and “Monitoring” groups grew steadily throughout the project as targeted outreach efforts resulted in raised awareness.

MailChimp was also used to create the monthly **EOSC-Life Newsletter** and to attract, track, and maintain EOSC-Life Newsletter subscribers throughout the project. The use of this helpful marketing automation and email marketing platform enabled us to achieve a nearly **500% increase** in the number of subscribers populating these stakeholder groups between Fall 2019 and Summer 2023. New stakeholders belonging to target groups were also attracted via the EOSC-Life social media channels, with a 2.5-time increase in followers seen on the **Twitter** channel and a nearly 10-time increase in **LinkedIn** followers over the same period.

2.3. Survey-based end-term assessment of communication and outreach efforts

At the project mid-term, WP representatives were asked to describe any outreach they performed themselves to achieve project communication objectives and to increase the number of stakeholders. This mid-term assessment revealed that the responding WPs felt that the most effective outreach methods were sending direct emails to interested communities, sharing information via Twitter, or presenting information in teleconferences or webinars.

In July 2023, WP representatives were again asked to describe outreach methods that they and/or their RI used to disseminate information about work package activities to stakeholder groups (i.e. using communication channels other than EOSC-Life channels) and to indicate how frequently these methods were used throughout the project.

Methods involving **direct contact** that proved most effective were:

- Face-to-face meetings,
- Virtual meetings (i.e. telephone or video conferences, webinars),
- Events (internal or with specific stakeholder groups), and

- Organisational events (project-related events like stakeholder meetings, working group meetings, Annual General Meetings, and hackathons)

Methods involving **digital contact** that proved most effective were:

- Targeted email messaging
- Social media (including retweeting/reposting of EOSC-Life outreach materials)
- Consortium member website (other than EOSC-Life)
- Electronic external newsletter (other than EOSC-Life Newsletter)
- Zenodo digital open repository use

And finally, methods involving **printed media** that proved most effective were:

- Project reports and deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Mid-term achievements brochure

One interesting successful development observed in the second project half is that project reports, deliverables, presentation slides, posters, and scientific publications that were uploaded to the open repository **Zenodo** were subsequently viewed and downloaded thousands of times, highlighting the high level of stakeholder attraction, impact, and engagement with EOSC-Life outputs achieved by using this outreach method.

3. End-term assessment of communication tools and strategies

Each of the communication tools used by EOSC-Life over the 4.5-year project period needed to be modified based on the results of the stakeholder mapping, WP representative feedback, and external factors. These tools were used at varying times and contexts to reach stakeholders based on the circumstances over this period. In Milestone **MS33**, we noted that unexpected changes in the political, scientific, and digital environments could affect the EOSC-Life project and decision-making in the WPs. The changes that occurred as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting effects on the project and decision-making illustrate this point.

One fascinating outcome of the changes that occurred over the project period is that WP representatives were forced by necessity to use a diversity of methods to attract, establish, and maintain contact with stakeholders and to perform general outreach. Outreach plans made in 2019 that involved direct, F2F contact with stakeholders in 2020 were initially postponed or cancelled due to the pandemic and, as pressure mounted to achieve WP objectives, moved online. WP10 provided outreach support by providing templates (virtual banners, Zoom backgrounds, advertisements) that could be used for online meetings, trainings, conferences, and webinars, plus other support for these events. The changes observed from 2020 to 2023 have, in turn, allowed us to gather valuable information on the effectiveness of outreach methods involving direct as opposed to virtual contact with these groups.

3.1. Developments in the use of communication tools

A concise overview of the communication tools that were initially identified as valuable in EOSC-Life is provided in the Communication Plan (**MS32**). Developments in the actual use of these tools

from August 2019 to February 2021 were described in **D10.1**. Below, we describe subsequent developments observed in communication tool use from March 2021 to July 2023, comparing these with the initial intentions described in the Communication Plan.

Direct contact

- *Face-to-face*: In 2019, WP representatives described **F2F meetings** as one of the most effective ways to communicate with stakeholders, explaining that feedback could be received directly. The intervening COVID-19 pandemic made F2F meetings generally impossible in 2020 and 2021, requiring those organising events (e.g. meetings, trainings, seminars, conferences) to fall back on (or, in some cases, learn how to use) virtual methods of contact. As (travel and contact) restrictions associated with the pandemic eased in 2022, some consortium members held F2F meetings as initially budgeted and planned in the EOSC-Life grant agreement, while others modified these plans to use virtual contact methods for reasons of safety, cost, or expediency.

- *Virtual meetings*: As noted above, **telephone or video conferences** replaced F2F meetings in 2020 and 2021 in most cases. Over this period, event organisers noted that such meetings were both cost-effective and allowed participants from a broader geographical range to join. WP representatives also quickly learned that feedback could also be directly received from participants in these online settings and that tools such as audio recording, video recording, and the chat feature could be used to support in-meeting interactions, provide meeting documentation, and enable individuals to later reference the materials.

- *Events*: In 2019, nearly all EOSC-Life events were internal, and materials associated with these events were not disseminated publicly, with the exceptions of the first AGM in Brussels and a few in-person technical training events. In 2020 and 2021, many events were postponed, rescheduled, or moved online, while some were cancelled. The outreach during this period of F2F → virtual meeting adaptation, therefore, was limited as compared to what had been intended, but online events occurred. In 2022 and 2023, as restrictions eased, the number of events (both F2F and virtual) increased considerably, in part because events postponed in 2021 were then held in 2022. The outreach in the two final project years consequently intensified, both from WP10 and the RIs themselves, which had the benefit of increasing the awareness of EOSC-Life in the identified stakeholder groups.

- *Organisational events*: **Project-related events** including stakeholder meetings, working group meetings (see Milestone MS34¹ for more information), Annual General Meetings, and hackathons introduced and/or supported dialogue with stakeholders in both F2F and virtual formats throughout the project period. Individuals who proved willing to actively serve as multipliers in certain stakeholder groups forwarded outreach materials as they were issued to their communities. Observations made in the second half of the project indicated that maintaining regular contact with WP representatives and leaders at each of the consortium partner organisations, as well as the communications officers at RIs and involved member organisations, greatly supported the promotion of the outreach materials.

Digital contact

- *Website*²: The website provided a stable, yet continually growing, means of disseminating project information. Early in the project, a special focus was directed toward addressing EOSC-Life

¹ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1ljxa51mv2PoCLgQJS2HBsmPgQ7RkF888/edit - slide=id.p1>

² <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

users' needs and expectations, clearly explaining the need for a digital space for the life sciences and how the WPs would help to create this. As the project progressed, the EOSC-Life Open Calls, Services (Demonstrators, Training, and Tools & Workflows) areas of the website were steadily populated with helpful links, videos, and materials. The creation of WP13 and WP14 in response to the COVID-19 pandemic correspondingly resulted in the addition of the COVID-19 Data Portal and Clinical Trials Data Repository resources to the Services area of the site. The Achievements and Resources areas highlight project outcomes and serve as a sustainable reference for website visitors. The News and Events area proved critical for disseminating information about upcoming meetings, events (trainings, webinars, conferences), Open Calls, and success stories, and provided ways for us to make stakeholders aware of related services offered by the participating RIs and other consortium partners.

Throughout the project, the website was used nearly as much by internal participants (e.g. access to Deliverables, publications, Open Calls) as by external participants (e.g. News and Events, Services). For this reason, much WP-specific information has been maintained on the site in the latter half of the project. As the project draws to a close, however, the pages are being steadily updated to reflect content that is of more sustainable use to external participants. The website structure has remained similar to the one originally outlined in our Communication Plan, although new pages have been added as needed (e.g. Achievements, Demonstrators, COVID-19 Data Portal, and Clinical Trials Data Repository). Some pages that were initially planned were abandoned (e.g. Platforms, Glossary), as experience indicated these were not necessary. The SEO tool YOST has ensured and continues to ensure search engine optimisation for the EOSC-Life site. The EOSC-Life website will be maintained until December 2029, and content of high importance for the RIs will be transferred to the sustainable LS RI website³.

- *External web space (Google Drive) for internal use:* The **EOSC-Life Google Drive** was established for internal communication (e.g. to promote the exchange of documents, provide templates, project calendar). Although the Drive continues to provide a useful space for providing access to important documents, templates, videos, images, and other materials, the use of the associated Google Calendar proved problematic, as information about events (meetings, trainings) was often shared too late to be of general use. The proliferation of outdated templates and document versions on the drive (as often occurs on any shared drive) also presented challenges.

- *Electronic external newsletter:* The **MailChimp** platform was used throughout the project to disseminate news about the EOSC-Life project and from consortium members via a **bi-monthly newsletter**, distributed to all consortium members and to external stakeholders who subscribed by email. As noted above, the use of this platform enabled us to populate, track, and maintain a stakeholder audience for the project. The content and success of the newsletter depended heavily on information provided by the WP representatives and the RIs (normally via the communications officer). Content in the newsletter has been linked to content on the EOSC-Life website or – in some cases – Twitter or LinkedIn posts insofar as possible to increase traffic on these communication channels. The opening rate of the newsletter has varied from 28–37%, which is generally considered good for such an outreach form.

- *Electronic internal newsflash:* EOSC-Life news and project information from the WP representatives and consortium members was also distributed internally via a **newsflash**, initially sent out bi-weekly, then weekly, and later bi-weekly again by email. The newsflash was used to

³ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

collect information from these members, and much of the newflash material reappeared in the bi-monthly newsletter, where appropriate. Opening rates of these emails were not tracked. This form of communication served as highly useful in promoting events of interest, passing on requests, providing work package updates, and receiving direct feedback from stakeholders.

- *Social media*: Because social media channels were identified as an efficient and cost-effective way to distribute information, EOSC-Life quickly established a **Twitter** account and a **LinkedIn** page. Throughout the project, EOSC-Life news has been posted by using these channels on a weekly basis, and posts from consortium partners and “Key Player” stakeholders have been reposted. The awareness of stakeholder categories listed in Table 5 has been raised by directly tagging specific individuals and organisations wherever possible and by using key hashtags, generally suggested by WP representatives. The social media accounts have been promoted through direct links on the project website, in email signatures, and by RIs that mention the EOSC-Life social media presence to their stakeholders. Traffic on these channels has grown steadily over time (see **D10.1** and section 3.4 below for statistics). These channels will be maintained for a period of at least one year beyond the project end date to support dissemination of project outcomes.

The decision was made early in the project to use the Life Science Research Infrastructures YouTube⁴ channel to post all EOSC-Life content under dedicated playlists, ensuring that the content would be sustained beyond the end of the project. This channel was not used heavily in 2019-2020, as most events and results were internal only. Currently, 33 videos resulting directly from EOSC-Life have been uploaded to this channel. Numerous other videos resulting from EOSC-Life supported activities with consortium partners are accessible via the website (e.g. Achievements, Training sections).

- *Targeted email messaging*: Direct emails have been sent out to stakeholders in specific categories as required, respecting GDPR guidelines. This outreach has generally been performed within each WP or together with the WPs to promote outcomes and events of interest to a specific community (e.g. cloud deployment, hackathons). These targeted emails seemed to elicit more responses than more general emails (i.e. sent out to the whole consortium or via MailChimp), because a more personalised form of address could normally be used, the subject line could be crafted specifically for the stakeholder group, and – if sent out by a consortium member directly to their contacts – was usually better received than, e.g. the newsletter. WP representatives noted that direct email was one of the most effective means of WP-specific outreach.

Printed media

The impact of this category was heavily influenced by the pandemic. Plans were made to produce posters, brochures, and giveaways for conference exhibitions in late spring/summer 2020, for example, but these were all cancelled, postponed, or moved online. As the restrictions eased, requests for printed material seemed to also drop off dramatically, in part due to changes in strategy, behaviour, and thought that occurred in 2021-2022 regarding the use (and usefulness) of this material. The request for a printed version of the final Achievements Brochure after August 2023 is one of the few requests for printed material made in the last two project years.

⁴ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWh-og5zm1J27aj-v2GG_fw/playlists

- *Public relations material*: A mid-term Achievements brochure was produced and made available via the EOSC-Life website for download. The final Achievements brochure is currently in preparation and will be disseminated in online and print forms at the end of the project. Templates for posters, slides, and PowerPoint presentations have been available in the internal EOSC-Life Google Drive for consortium member use since 2020, along with all branding information (e.g. colours, fonts, logos). These templates have been modified and used by WP representatives for a wide variety of dissemination purposes, ranging from advertising events to presenting outcomes at events (e.g. conferences, meetings, seminars, webinars, trainings).

- *Press release*: Consortium members were asked to follow all procedures regarding press releases, i.e. to write these as national and international non-scientific articles and adapt them to meet the needs of relevant stakeholders to effectively convey the project's vision, Open Calls, or other sustainable outcomes. Three press releases were sent out in the first half of the project (project launch, COVID-19 Data Portal launch, and publication of RIs offering resources for COVID-19 research), and two are planned at the end of the project (highlighting the sustainable outcomes and connections between EOSC-Life and other funded projects that have adopted EOSC-Life tools or workflows). RIs and other consortium members also produced press releases throughout the project in accordance with these procedures to describe funding support for joint efforts (e.g. EMBRC workflow for marine Genomic Observatories data analysis).

- *Scientific publications*: The scientific outcomes of EOSC-Life have been steadily published in the form of Open Access articles in peer-reviewed journals as they have emerged. Information about these articles has been primarily disseminated to stakeholders via a dedicated Deliverables and Publications page on the website⁵ (reference obtained from the EC Portal), social media channels, newsletters, and newsflashes. When sharing news of the publication via social media, authors have been tagged, and appropriate hashtags have been used to attract the attention of relevant stakeholders to promote broad dissemination. When sharing the news via the newsflash and newsletter, a link to the website (news item or publication) has been provided to promote dissemination among subscribers (external and internal) and to increase traffic on the EOSC-Life website.

- *Project reports and deliverables*: All deliverables and project reports are public; thus, they are published on the website via the same Deliverables and Publications page described above, hyperlinked to a Zenodo⁶ record, which ensures that they are findable via a DOI beyond the end of the project. These public documents inform the stakeholder communities on progress and achievements of EOSC-Life and have been promoted via the social media channels and in the newsletters and newsflashes throughout the project.

3.2. Application of the Strategic Marketing and Communication Plan

In Milestone **M32**, we clearly described the primary goal of WP10, namely, to create connections among the stakeholders in ways that would support the creation of an open, collaborative digital space for the life sciences in Europe. To achieve this complex goal, effective two-way communication needed to be established with these stakeholders. At the beginning of the project, it was as imperative to listen to and understand our stakeholders' needs and strategies as

⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/resources/project-deliverables/>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/>

it was to describe how EOSC-Life would work, communicate progress toward project goals, and highlight the opportunities created by the resulting research outcomes (i.e. success stories) as the project progressed.

An initial internal Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis for the project conducted in 2019 (**MS32**) revealed the strengths and weaknesses of the project, as well as opportunities and threats surrounding it, in terms of communication with stakeholders. This analysis enabled us to set specific targets for improving and strengthening this communication and address these. Specifically, time and resources were invested in the first two project years to achieve impacts in the following areas:

- The website was used as the central communication point for the EU and the project partners
- Social media accounts were created to communicate with all stakeholders
- Mailing lists and emailing templates were created to inform the EU and project members
- Project partners and the network were asked to disseminate information via social media and email
- Key project messages or spinoffs on the current slogan, as well as accompanying images, were created and used to reach the different stakeholder groups or subjects
- The newsletter and dedicated mailings were used to announce open calls

In addition, we proactively used our strengths in communication to address potential hurdles as the project progressed, including:

- Communicating project progress and results to all policymakers
- Using the organisational structure, seminars, and networks to communicate with the RIs and researchers, to scale up the available data, contract demonstrators for test sessions and open calls, and to gain trust on data use collected by others (i.e. emphasising data integrity)

We recognised that certain areas would present specific challenges, and that resources would need to be invested to achieve positive outcomes. These investments included the creation of the website, social media accounts, mailing lists and emailing templates, dissemination templates (e.g. for seminars, webinars, other events), and press releases. Throughout the project, our efforts have steadily intensified to ensure effective communication with project partners, national RI partners, as well as facilities that are RI partners but not formal EOSC-Life consortium members, RI users, prospective users in the broader life sciences community, EOSC contributors (mainly e-Infrastructures and RIs in other domains), science policymakers, and industry partners. To communicate with these users, partners, and other stakeholders, EOSC-Life has used its website as the central dissemination tool. The EOSC-Life social media channels, a digital newsletter, press releases and press contacts, and events have also supported these efforts.

3.3. Goals / KPIs

The Strategic Marketing and Communication Plan set initial targets that could be used to measure the success of communication in the project's first year. These target numbers were based on similar size EU projects in similar fields and reported in **D10.1**. An examination of the status on 9 February 2021 indicated that social media targets had been overestimated and the use of our website had been vastly underestimated.

Based on feedback from the Midterm Review Report, SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Results-oriented, Time-bound) KPIs were added and monitored for the remainder of the project. These monitoring results are shown below in Table 6.

KPI	Goal by 1 March 2022	Status by 1 March 2022	Status by 1 July 2023
Twitter followers	1372	922	1680
Twitter – link clicks per month	67	0 ^A	36
Twitter - retweets per month	65	0 ^B	138
LinkedIn page followers	305	235	696 ^C
YouTube videos posted	18	12	31
YouTube - total views	222	111	233
Newsletter subscribers	601	534	558
Website - unique page views	47,010	33,454	79,782 ^D
Press releases sent	1	3	3

Table 6: Updated SMART KPIs

^A Gap in Twitter posting due to personnel change at BBMRI-ERIC

^B Gap in Twitter posting due to personnel change at BBMRI-ERIC

^C Contrary to expectations reported in D10.1, a steep increase in followers was observed in the 2nd project period.

^D Contrary to expectations reported in D10.1, new visitors viewed the EOSC-Life website at a steady rate (rather than a decreasing rate) in the 2nd project period.

These statistics reveal several interesting trends in the second half of the project. First, the increased communication efforts invested to promote the website and YouTube videos via social media, the newflash, and the newsletter were rewarded not only by achieving the mid-term goals set but by exceeding them. Second, Twitter engagement proved useful for reinforcing communication and the exchange of information among the EOSC-Life consortium members, and especially among the Research Infrastructures, but the usefulness of this platform has been called into question by recent changes in the platform and resulting instability in the algorithms used. Third, although WP leaders had noted at the mid-term assessment point that most main end users for this project were generally not engaged on LinkedIn, the efforts invested to continue to disseminate policy-related content, Open Calls, and content of general interest via this social media channel were richly rewarded. In fact, this channel gained more than 200 new followers in the final project year alone, indicating that it is both an effective and promising medium for future professional communication with stakeholders.

Abbreviations

ABS	Access and Benefit Sharing
BBSRC	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council
CA	Consortium Agreement
CORBEL	Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Ensuring Life-Sciences Services
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019 by SARS-C

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DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
DoA	Description of Action
ENVRI	ENVironmental Research Infrastructures
ENVRI-FAIR	ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building FAIR services
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESCAPE	European Symposium on Computer-Aided Process Engineering
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EMBRC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre
EU	European Union
F2F	Face-to-face
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
H2020	Horizon Programme 2020
KPI	Key performance indicator
LS	Life Science
LS RI	Life Science Research Infrastructure
NFAIS	National Federation of Advanced Information Services
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
OERTC	Organisation Européenne de Recherche sur le Traitement du Cancer
PaNOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud
RI	Research Infrastructure
SEAB	Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Results-oriented, Time-bound
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization
WHO	World Health Organization
WMA	World Medical Association
WP	Work Package

Delivery and Schedule

The deliverable is delayed: No

Adjustments

Adjustments made: None

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